

A PERCEPTUAL STUDY ON DYNAMICAL FORM IN MUSIC

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ABSTRACT

The concept of dynamical form is presented as a dimension of music perception. Dynamical form refers to the subjective perception of temporal events in music (*explosive, fading out, rising* etc.). In a behavioral experiment listeners were asked to categorize musical excerpts varying in musical period, tonality, instrumentation, and acoustic features while attending to their dynamical form. Data indicates that subjects are sensitive to dynamical forms, but were particularly sensitive to a specific one (*suspense*). We also discuss a method of categorizing dynamical forms in terms of force dynamics.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we introduce the concept of dynamical form as a fundamental dimension of musical experience. The concept of dynamical form is not related to 'dynamics' in the sense of loudness in music, but pertains to the ways in which musical change is subjectively perceived. Dynamical forms may be described in language by adjectives such as *rising, fading out, explosive, surging, lively, tentative, rushing* etc. Previous work relevant to dynamical form (such as [12],[15]) has typically examined it in relation to musical emotion, but we argue that it should be considered as a distinct dimension. For instance, a musical passage experienced as *angry* may be angry in an eruptive or slowly rising fashion.

Dynamical forms are general cross-modal patterns of experience grounded in bodily-kinesthetic experience. They have been studied in infant psychology ([7]) and suggested to be among the earliest and most fundamental forms of experience in humans. In this context they are referred to as *vitality contours* or *vitality affects*, and pertain to the way in which temporal events are felt and categorized. Some music theorists have suggested their relevance to musical experience (e.g., [18]), but experimental work on this is sparse (although [1] may be said to be related).

On the other hand, experimental work in psychoacoustics indicates that recognition of events or gestures (e.g., [4],[21],[28]), as well as physical properties of the sound source (e.g., [3],[5],[8],[22],[24]) are of fundamental relevance to auditory perception in general. Gestural aspects have also been suggested to be of relevance to music perception (see e.g. [2]). However, we consider gestures to be an instance of the more general category of

dynamical form. A gesture may be experienced as having a certain dynamic form - e.g. eruptive or toning out - but dynamical forms may also be experienced in relation to physical events (an eruptive volcano or the fading out of a river flow).

2. TAXONOMY OF DYNAMICAL FORMS

With the above in mind, we can provisionally sketch a classification scheme of 3 general and independent dimensions of musical experience: (a) emotion or valence, (b) source properties, and (c) dynamical form. Each dimension gives rise to linguistic descriptions that may be used to illustrate them:

Emotion	Source	Dynamical form
Mourning	Crunchy	Fleeting
Angry	Heavy	Drawn out
Joyful	Compact	Explosive
Proud	Creaking	Floating
Gentle	Dirty	Expanding
Lamenting	Wet	Struggling

Table 1. Verbal descriptors of basic listening dimensions

The studies in music psychology most relevant to dynamical form are studies of musical 'tension' or 'force' ([10],[11],[23]). This may refer to either patterns of tension and relaxation in harmonic structure, or to the felt presence of tension due to rhythmic complexity, acoustic dissonance, melodic attraction, etc. A number of experimental studies have used a continuous response method to have subjects rate the amount of perceived tension in the course of music listening (e.g., [9],[11],[25]).

Unlike tension considered as a continuous variable, dynamical forms are semantic units of perceived events or states. While music may be experienced as a continuous flow of tension, we argue that dynamical forms arise from the experience of interaction between opposing tension or force tendencies. In physical experience, we constantly perceive interactions between objects having given force tendencies. We may perceive a man leaning against an unlocked door as an unstable scene where

there is a balance between the force applied by the weight of the man and the resisting force of the door. Perception of scenes like this possesses force dynamical structure in the sense described by L. Talmy ([14]) from the point of view of language. We will suggest that dynamical forms in music can also be categorized in terms of force dynamics.

2.1 A dynamical model of force semantics

Force dynamical patterns are characterized in terms of two interacting force entities with conflicting force tendencies. In the scene with the man leaning against a door there are two conflicting force tendencies. We perceive the man as potentially moving, but being withheld by the stronger force tendency (towards rest) of the door. Force dynamical patterns are constituted by the two opposing force tendencies (one towards action or motion, and one towards rest), and by the balance of strength between these tendencies. Perceiving (and describing) the scene also incorporates a certain perspective. For instance, one would tend to see the man leaning against the door from the perspective of the man (rather than viewing the door as being leaned-upon by the man).

Four basic patterns describing steady-state force positions arise from the possible interactions of these structural elements (force tendencies, balance of strength) and the perspective. Consider instead, for instance, a man that keeps standing in spite of a heavy wind blowing upon him. In this scene, the structural roles have switched: now the man has a tendency towards rest that is stronger than the opposing force tendency of the wind (towards action).

In addition to these steady-state patterns, corresponding changing-state patterns exist. If the door breaks and the man falls down, then there is a change in the structural elements: the weaker force tendency of the door is removed and the man's tendency towards motion is actualized. If the wind knocks the man off his feet, then the changing-state pattern is that of a shift in the balance of strength between the two force entities.

Such semantical force patterns have been described by L. Talmy within cognitive linguistics ([14]). They are considered to be fundamental cognitive forms underlying our understanding of basic phenomena such as causation and modality. In the present context, we will suggest that force dynamical patterns can be described at a general level as a dynamical system. Consider a one-dimensional dynamical system with 2 control parameters:

$$\dot{x} = h + rx - x^3 \quad (1)$$

where h and r represent the magnitudes of the two interacting forces. A stable state of the system correspond to a given force tendency (towards action or rest). The system undergoes bifurcations when the two force parameters are varied continuously. Bifurcations occur around a cusp shape in the (r,h) -plane (see figure 1). Inside the cusp, there are two asymmetrically stable states (a conflict of forces), while there is only one outside. In Figure 1 below, stable states are illustrated by potential functions of

the flow in given states (stable states corresponding to local minima). A 'ball' in the potential minimum indicates that the state is realized. The realized states are seen from the point of view of the first force entity.

Figure 1. Stability diagram of the (r,h) -plane. Stable states are indicated by potential minima. Stippled arrows indicate the initial state of a given realized state.

The model follows the delay convention. This means that a stable state (a force tendency) persists until it is destroyed. Outside the cusp there is a single stable state corresponding to action or rest (corresponding to the dominating force). When entering the cusp, a conflict between two potential states (rest/action) arises. At the midline ($h=r$) there is a balance of strength between the forces, and trajectories across this line correspond to transitions between action and rest.

The force parameters (h,r) correspond to the perception of tension. Although these vary continuously there are only four qualitatively different conflicting states of the system (force dynamical steady state patterns $a-d$). There may be a tendency towards rest ($a-b$) or towards action ($c-d$). The alternative potential state is either more ($a-c$) or less ($b-d$) stable resulting in action ($a-d$) or rest ($b-c$). For instance, in state c we have the situation described above of the man leaning against a door. There is a tendency towards motion but a stronger tendency towards rest (causing rest). The man standing in spite of the wind appears as state b (a stronger tendency towards rest). We may readily extend the model to encompass changing-state patterns (where a transition between action and rest takes place). This corresponds to trajectories either across the cusp (e.g., caused or blocked actions), or across the midline (changed balance of strengths, e.g. trapped action, overcoming, etc.).

Dynamical forms can be categorized as generalized force dynamical patterns. This means that a dynamical form can be categorized into specified semantic types or dynamic 'archetypes'. The man leaning against the door (state *c*) corresponds to dynamical forms expressing *suspense* or *tension* (a state of suppressed action). Force magnitudes may vary continuously but the way in which they interact with other forces gives rise to a limited number of patterns. In relation to music we argue that continuously perceived tension gives rise to discrete semantic patterns (dynamical forms) that can be characterized by their force dynamical structure.

In Figure 2 below, dynamical forms of different steady-state types are shown in the bifurcation diagram described by verbal labels:

Figure 2. Verbal labels indicating dynamical forms in the stability diagram

3. EXPERIMENT

3.1 Experimental design

A behavioral experiment was designed to examine whether listeners are sensitive to dynamical forms in music. Subjects performed two different listening tasks on 16 short musical excerpts of existing performed music. The excerpts were chosen by the authors to represent a broad variation on a number of musical parameters: tonality, mode, instrumentation, genre, and period of production. The excerpts could all be considered 'classical music', but included both tonal and atonal music, older and more recent music, as well as different instrumentations. Excerpts of 10-15 seconds were taken from the following works:

No	Composer	Work	Tonality	Instr.	Year
1	Liszt	Paganini etude no. 2 (La Campanella)	tonal (mi)	piano	1851
2	Mahler	Symphony no. 3, 6th movement	tonal (ma)	orch.	1896
3	Messiaen	Vingt regards sur l'enfant jesus, no. X	atonal	piano	1944
4	Prokofiev	Romeo & Juliet, finale	atonal	orch.	1935
5	Alva Noto	Attack (UTP_)	atonal	orch.	2009
6	Beethoven	Piano Sonata, op. 31, 1st movement	tonal (mi)	piano	1803
7	Debussy	Preludes for piano, no. 3 (Animé)	tonal (ma)	piano	1910
8	Grisey	Modulations	atonal	orch.	1978
9	Abrahamsen	Boogie Woogie	atonal	piano	1983
10	Bartok	String quartet no. 4, 4th movement	atonal	orch.	1929
11	Brahms	Capriccio, op. 116, no. 2	tonal (mi)	piano	1878
12	Tchaikovsky	Slavonic march, op. 31	tonal (mi)	orch.	1852
13	Barry	The sinking of Devonshire (Soundtrack)	tonal (mi)	orch.	1997
14	Ligeti	Atmosphères	atonal	orch.	1961
15	Schubert	Piano sonata, D784, 1st movement	tonal (mi)	piano	1815
16	Smetana	On the seashore	tonal (mi)	piano	1861

Table 2. List of excerpts used in the experiment

In choosing the musical excerpts, the authors found 4 different dynamic forms to be most salient. These may be described as (i) *overcoming, climaxing* (no. 1-4), (ii) *eruptive, bursting* (no. 5-8), (iii) *striving, struggling* (no. 9-12), and (iv) *suspense, tense* (no. 13-16). These correspond to four different force dynamical patterns, as discussed above. Forms i-ii are changing-state patterns in which there is either an overcoming (i) or removal (ii) of an antagonistic force. Forms iii-iv correspond to steady-state patterns *c* and *d* respectively in figure 1 (also indicated in figure 2).

However, subjects were not informed of those forms. They were simply instructed to attend to dynamical form in general. The concept was introduced to subjects beforehand by two different examples of dynamical forms in other excerpts. The question of interest was whether subjects would group the excerpts according to perceived dynamical form across major musical categories (tonality, period, instrumentation).

Fourteen subjects of varying musical background participated in the experiment. The experiment consisted of two separate parts. In the first part of the experiment, similarity ratings were obtained. Subjects were presented with triads of excerpts. In each trial, subjects were asked to indicate which two excerpts of the three were most similar, and to rate their similarity on a discrete rating scale (1-7). Each subject was not presented with all possible combinations of excerpts, but the between-subject order of presentation was fixed so that the subjects collectively heard all combinations. The second part of the experiment consisted of a free clustering task. All 16 excerpts could be accessed, and subjects were asked to group each of them into four groups or less. They were also asked to write word labels indicating how they perceived a given excerpt. The subjects were allowed to write as many labels they liked. They gave between 1-3 labels for each excerpt.

3.2 Results

A mean similarity matrix between each excerpt was created for each task. For the first task, similarities simply corresponded to ratings. In the free clustering task, the similarities were calculated as percentage overlap between groups ([19]). The matrices produced by the different tasks were highly correlated, even though the subjects were presented with different subsets of excerpt combinations in the first task. Consequently, the two matrices are collapsed in the following analysis.

A hierarchical cluster analysis (single-linkage) was performed on the mean similarity data. Four groups are seen in the analysis, indicated in figure 3. These groups were - interestingly - not identical to the ones hypothesized by the authors. For each group, the word labels given in the free clustering task were semantically highly related across subjects. Labels representative of these semantically related categories are shown next to the groups in figure 3.

The found group structure was compared with a number of factors that could be suspected to influence the perception of similarity between excerpts. A correlational analysis was performed, and only instrumentation was found to correlate significantly with the behavioral data. Neither period of production nor tonality or mode correlated significantly with the data. A number of psychoacoustic parameters of potential perceptual relevance were obtained by computerized analysis of the audio data. This included energy RMS, roughness ([27]), spectral irregularity ([13]), Mel-frequency cepstrum coefficients, tempo, flatness of the temporal envelope, and slope of the spectral centroid. All of these were found to have low correlation ($< .24$) with the behavioral data.

Figure 3. Hierarchical cluster analysis of behavioral data with verbal labels given by subjects

3.3 Discussion

The results suggest that listeners when instructed to attend to dynamical forms, group musical excerpts across musical periods, genres, tonality, and acoustic features. The separation in terms of instrumentation into two broad groups (piano/orchestra) does not account for all variation in the similarity data. This could suggest that the subjects are in fact sensitive to dynamical forms that are independent of these factors. The verbal labels given by subjects also indicated their sensitivity to dynamical forms.

Interestingly, the similarities perceived by subjects were different from the ones suspected by the authors. A given musical excerpt may possess a number of dynamical forms simultaneously. For instance, excerpts 5 and 8 contain sudden differences in instrumentation and loudness that may be experienced as *explosive* or *eruptive*. But they also have an undefined harmonic structure that may cause them to be experienced as *tense* or expressing a state of *suspense* at a more global level. Apparently, this second quality appeared more salient than the first.

The moderate clarity of the behavioral data and the resulting clustering may be caused by the fact that subjects attended to dynamical forms that are of similar type. Three of the four groups (II-IV) have identical force dynamical structure. They are different instances of force dynamical pattern *c*: a force tendency towards motion with a stronger opposing force. Subjects thus preferably attend to dynamical forms expressing a state of tension or suspense. Only group I has different force dynamical structure (a changing event pattern), expressing a transition from motion to rest (*ending, overcoming*).

It is interesting to observe the apparent saliency of pattern *c* in music. Theories of musical listening are often based on the idea that music is subjectively perceived as

motion ([16],[17],[20],[26]). The salient dynamical form found in this experiment, however, is not perceived as motion, but as an interaction of forces resulting in rest as suspended motion. In this way we may argue that force dynamical structure represents a more fundamental way of conceiving the subjective nature of music perception.

The similarity of perceived dynamical forms makes it difficult draw conclusions on the basis of these behavioral results. We would suggest that additional experiments with other musical excerpts, perhaps reflecting an even broader range of musical variation, is needed to gain more information about the perception of dynamical forms.

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